

Brian's Sordid Encounters with Micky Flanagan **by Brian Paul Kaess**

Brian Paul Kaess, growing up in Chicago's Edgewater neighborhood, knew the Flanagan Family as schoolmates or 'chums' at St. Gregory Elementary School & Lane Tech High School. Patrick Flanagan and Brian were in the same graduating class at St. Greg's ('81) and Lane ('85), with Micky Flanagan being the elder brother and Sean Flanagan being the younger. Brian was more friends with Patrick and Sean than Micky, but Micky also acted as a Mentor and they did spend time together wargaming, etc.; There was also Thomas Flanagan, but Brian had little contact with him. Micky's dad worked at the *Chicago Tribune*, and his mom was typical red-haired Irish. They lived on Catalpa ave. in a residential area in West Edgewater.

Micky, who was on a Loyola University Chicago Army ROTC Scholarship, urged me to apply to West Point, not just New Mexico Military Insititute, but I later took this as some sort of grooming. Micky of course, was Michael Patrick Flanagan (R-IL), future U.S. Congressman and 'giant killer' who had dethroned Dan Rostenkowski (D-IL) with an upset victory in 1994.

Micky had mentioned having had sex with underage 'Mexican' girls but my knowledge of pedophile laws at the time was nil, so I barely payed attention.

But there were three incidents in my relationship with Micky that were unnerving and I will now set them forth here:

1. In Spring 1984, Micky asked me if would help him by allowing him to take nude photos of myself, for a fee of \$100. This was not at my initiative, but his. I was 16 at the time. He said these photos were for a Loyola University Chicago Photography class, but this seemed almost like a calculated ruse. At the time, I was naive and agreed, and I later met him at his apartment for the photo shoot. He had me sit on a chair nude while he took the photos. The shoot lasted about 20 minutes or so, and, after it ended, Micky patted me on the shoulder, said 'good job' and handed me a \$100.
2. In late Summer 1984, I was driving with Micky on a rural road or state highway near Fort Sill, Oklahoma, possibly in/near Lawton, Oklahoma. Micky was going through Army Field Artillery OBC at Ft. Sill and Patrick Flanagan and I had visited him in his BOQ room on the base. We also met other Army officers who seemed enthusiastic that we were interested in serving in the Army. Micky even took me to the Officer's Club on base, and who knows, maybe he felt he had 'payed for it.' In any case, during the ride on the rural road or highway, he turned to me and said, 'It's been a long ride, how about I give you a blowjob?' This was clearly inappropriate since I was a minor and I stated immediately 'no thanks.' There I was , alone with a some dude who I thought before was normal, but now wanted some 'gay action!' Things nonetheless stayed calm and later, Patrick and I drove on to New Mexico, even waking up one bright, orange, dawn morning in New Mexico with bats on our windshield! We interviewed at New Mexico Military Institute and returned home to Chicago in late July or early August 1984.

3. In January 1992, I was a student at Northeastern Illinois University, living with the Aguda Family in East Edgewater in Chicago. Micky had already stopped by a couple of times before, just to have drinks at the local bar. No biggie. He liked cruising around in a white convertible and was busy in his last year at Loyola School. I think he had just taken the Bar exam when he called me on the phone, and said, 'I want you to do something for me,.. I want to pay you \$700 for you to perform oral sex on me.' This was classic Micky! I immediately hung up the phone, and told Michelle Aguda, Chris Aguda's sister about it, who was standing nearby. I never went near the Flanagan's again. I think stress wasn't helpful for Micky.

This may have been straight from the Republican 'playbook' but who knows? I thought it was best to just stay away from weirdos who are trying to turn the people gay. My friend John Toth and brother Garret Kaess joked about it and both said to me: 'No more KP, boy!' I told Dr. Sneep about it in the E.R. during Micky's election and he seemed amused, and it was a bit of a novelty for some at Northeastern who wanted me to go with my girlfriend Azra Bojic to the press about it. Years later, I submitted my story to the *New York Times* and they were happy enough to take my notes. I also chatted with a reporter from the *Daily Southtown* and a female reporter at the *Chicago Tribune*. But this scandal never even made the back pages. I suspected that sex scandal stories against Congress, often get thrown 'under the rug.' If Russia had its Beria, then America had its Micky! End of Story.